

THE [*SELF-*]LEARNING CHALLENGES FACED BY DISTANCE LEARNING STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses the issue of distance education and its peculiarities, as well as the demands it presents regarding the need for mastery in the field of didactics by students who choose this model of academic training. Its scientific relevance lies in promoting a solid argument about a training model that still lacks clarification regarding its didactic guidelines, what can and should be provided to the student to achieve success in their educational endeavor. Its social relevance lies in presenting to the general public the challenges that it brings together, while clarifying that its epistemological and phenomenological basis seeks to prepare the individual to act with confidence and professionalism in their chosen field of study. This is a bibliographical essay, prepared based on the author's experience as a teacher working in this modality and based on the scientific work of classical authors on the subject. What is explored in this work is the condition that treating distance education as opposed to face-to-face education, without considering the learning possibilities specific to each of them, is to act in tune with a binary, irrational and uncritical way of thinking, revealing itself to be disharmonious with the processes of sociological development, which is another paradox, because the more possibilities for adjustments in the processes are considered, the more it becomes necessary to seek to deepen the investigations and methodologies that allow greater transparency regarding the results.

Keywords: Distance Education. Didactics. Capacity for analysis, interpretation and synthesis.

INTRODUCTION

Distance education, or distance learning as a euphemism, refers to teaching where the student does not need to be physically present in a formal educational environment with teachers and classmates. The fact is, all learning occurs at a distance from the subject matter and its psychology, because knowledge can only be produced through analyzing the student's response to being influenced by some agent; that is, the student is in the present, but that which actually teaches them is in the past.

Having made this initial approach, what is important is to highlight to students dedicated to distance learning the need to understand the self-directed learning challenges that are naturally and pertinently imposed on them in relation to their chosen field of education. It is important to emphasize that didactics, far more than referring to teaching and learning processes, is linked to learning to be, to a highly complex subjective issue that affects the individual. It is this understanding of their intrinsic reality that leads them to go further, to surpass themselves, and not only to seek or even find knowledge, but to create new ways of producing knowledge from the analysis of the reality that surrounds them, in an attempt to solve the problems that society presents as challenges.

distance education is most questioned, this is, paradoxically, the greatest challenge posed to the students themselves. The reason this condition is highlighted as a paradox is because the object of action is simultaneously the object of intervention and a reflection of the self-discipline applied to their search for information and understanding of how to become excellent on their own, and how this empirical result can be treated as a strategic and methodological model for future generations of students.

In the face-to-face modality, where, apparently, as has been advocated, the student's contact with knowledge is greater [*this being highlighted as the teacher*], this condition becomes a danger and an end in itself; because, when confronted with some subjective question, be it in the form of a word or even a scientific dispute, the student tends to direct their state of doubt to the teacher, taking them as the one who *must* answer them about such a question, clarifying it, since, by force of the social contract, they are prevented from leaving the room at their pleasure and going to the library in search of an author or text that can shed light on the problem. In contrast, the distance learning student, given their autonomy in their studies—even to the point of using the term "independence," provided it is properly interpreted—is recognized as the author of their own study pace and dynamics. When confronted with an idea that proves to be beyond their comprehension or mastery, this individual can resort to various media to resolve their doubts and/or clarify their thoughts, expanding their vocabulary and becoming the author of their own investigative condition, directly and solely responsible for expanding their intellectual knowledge and logical mastery of objective and subjective situations.

distance learning process, the tutor or professor has the obligation to guide the student on the first steps towards knowledge within the thematic field they have chosen to pursue as a professional career. From there, it is up to the student to unravel the obscure and challenging points presented and/or discovered as they progress in their studies. The more disciplined they are, the deeper and broader their knowledge becomes, understanding that all science is, *par*

excellence , inter- and multidisciplinary, allowing for a heuristic view of and from the world in which their cognitive and epistemological interests are applied.

What needs to be clarified is that treating distance education in opposition to face-to-face education, without considering the learning possibilities peculiar to each, is, once again, acting in line with a binary way of thinking, always out of harmony with the processes of sociological development. This is another paradox, because the more possibilities for adjustments in the processes are considered, the more necessary it becomes to seek deeper investigations and methodologies that allow for greater transparency regarding the results. Ending up trapped in a Cartesian and positivist market logic, captured by the ideology of the diploma as the foundation of knowledge, does not prove to be the solution to the problem of distance learning . This functions as an attempt to justify the blame for the intellectual decline currently being experienced, blaming a teaching-learning modality; this is equivalent to throwing the baby out with the bathwater.

Distance education requires learning strategies and an evaluation of its methods, which means that the State, through academia, needs to invest in empirical studies that demonstrate where and how to apply its intellectual and creative development capabilities to produce results consistent with what is expected to meet sociological demands at all levels.

DISTANCE EDUCATION

Distance education is offered in a modality where the student does not need to be regularly present in the classroom with their teachers and mentors. This does not mean they are obligated to study every day for a set number of hours in order to acquire the knowledge necessary for their intellectual development. It is a revolutionary approach that has allowed many citizens, over time, access to higher academic education, even at prestigious universities. This clarifies that distance education, in itself, represents a cognitive and intellectual investment of exponential merit, with individual effort being proportional to the desire for self-improvement that defines each person's life.

It is thus assumed that, “Distance Education is the educational modality in which the didactic-pedagogical mediation in the teaching and learning processes occurs with the use of information and communication technologies, with students and teachers developing educational activities in different places or times” (Brazil, 2005, n.p.), respecting the dictates foreseen by law for the occurrence of face-to-face moments, with activities previously determined. Even if this quote seems to define a concept for Distance Education , and the

publication of decree 5622 of 2005 is intended to be interpreted as a regulation for this modality, it may well come close to achieving this in the legislative field, leaving open the spaces for its pedagogical characterization and didactic functionality.

From a pedagogical point of view, what we always have is an abstract idea that the role of education, in general, is to build a citizen with a critical spirit, engaged in the struggle for a just and humane society. Nothing interesting, because the principle of Pedagogy is the integral formation of the human being, and with this paradigm, the notion of the starting and ending point in the integration of the individual with their most particular interests has been lost, which, in many cases, is simply to achieve knowledge and mastery of the content of the science they have chosen as a professional career.

Therefore, this attempt to humanize someone who only wants to become a technician, without explaining the strict meaning of the term, gradually causes students with high learning potential to literally distance themselves from the courses and their pedagogical guidelines, because they understand that everything presented there is nothing more than utopia and a waste of time that could be better spent. It should be clarified that the expression "*humanize*" means transforming someone into someone who can reconcile professional practice with some event of social transformation, innovating in favor of those who live dependent on public policies. This is a pragmatic approach related to each specific professional field, considering that every human being, regardless of their area of expertise, yearns for recognition in their field of cognitive and intellectual investment and endeavor.

In terms of teaching methods, distance education falls short in its academic training policy because it denies students their political-pedagogical project, in which they must prove their autonomy through the presentation of empirical results, demonstrating mastery in their oral explanations, fluency in their written theoretical productions, in their technical and scientific approaches, and dynamism in their pragmatic attitudes. In this process, the teacher's role is to demand that the student present themselves and their projects with expertise, showing skill and competence in defending them before the audience.

Therefore, while the issue of legal regulation is necessary to provide security for students in all areas, particularly in the field of professional activity, attempting to prevent any type of discrimination, it is not sufficient to prevent the exclusion of graduates due to possible poor technical, academic, and scientific training.

The market, in its eagerness and imminence to attract dividends—which, in education, sees the student as a potential source of monetary income—fails to reveal to the student their role in their academic journey. Instead of being easier [*or less difficult*] than that of their peers

attending in-person classes, it is neither one nor the other; it is unique, with very specific and defined demands, where no perspective on personal and cognitive development can be overlooked. In this context, an individual excels through their intrinsic effort, creativity, and demonstrated performance, not only in their chosen career field but also in other areas that, directly and/or indirectly, can aid in the construction of their intellect and personal transformation.

Distance education represents a radical transformation in learning processes, without any differentiation in teaching determinisms, because the content is made available to the student, who is responsible for seeking it out and understanding the most complex subjects, without being bound to the praxis of their teachers. Thus, they are forced to produce their own praxis, their own way of exploring the real world, using the tools that can best provide them with the knowledge they need to overcome their cognitive and intellectual deficiencies and still achieve their individual academic goals.

When academic training became a possibility outside the walls of the traditional Academy, this achievement was not well received by the scientific community, which had always believed that knowledge could only be attained if the student were subjected to the sacred rituals that take place solely within its closed spaces. This generated a distorted idea of knowledge acquisition, in which knowledge ceases to be something achieved through experience and contact with the object, and the interpretation and consequent understanding of its psychology, becoming instead a fusional transfer between apprentice and master.

Distance education breaks with this paradigm and freely grants human access to nature and the learning opportunities it offers, according to individual interests and effort. This puts an end to the academic hegemony of believing in the osmotic transmission of knowledge. What stands out is that learning through distance education is a very intense *self-directed* learning challenge, requiring students to delve much deeper into independent study and interpretations that *might otherwise* be less demanding. The result of this epistemological effort is revealed in the phenomenological condition of a deeper, broader, and more solid learning experience, opening space for more incisive questioning in the field of science.

Self-Learning Challenges of Distance Learning Students

In distance learning, students are subject to challenges that exceed their previously known capabilities; that is, they will have to develop other, more complex skills that will require greater depth in the semantic fields of other disciplines, simply because, logically, they will not

be able to consult a specialist in such areas every time they encounter a question that seems obscure and difficult to understand. This epistemological breadth of knowledge is necessary so that they can analyze texts, *cases*, and phenomena with a broad characterization of logical thinking, associating what they find with objective reality, instead of interpreting it from a purely subjective point of view.

This form of study is necessary because the student will have to develop their own didactic mechanisms; that is, they will have to create a teaching method that satisfies their learning desires and knowledge needs to overcome the difficulties inherent in understanding natural and artificial phenomena, deducing facts and producing syntheses. Didactics refers to learning to be; therefore, the distance learning student must learn to find within themselves the motivation to advance in their studies, both theoretical and empirical, and become able to interpret the experiences to which they are subject.

It must always be clarified that the aim of education is to provide a holistic view of reality, seeking to distance oneself, as much as possible, from binary thinking, in which everything is determined by what is believed and anything presented as the opposite is treated as false; therefore, an object of contempt and aversion. This is a condition that cannot be part of the spirit of the distance learning student, because by being at the mercy of their own motivation, if they associate things through binary determinism, they will lose their potential capacity to perform comprehensive semantic readings of reality, leading to the construction of irrational, passionate, and illogical thought. With intellectual construction, the aim is to develop critical thinking, understood as the ability to ask broad questions arising from their doubts, experiences, and investigative pursuits. Hanscomb (2023, pp. 98-99) clarifies that, "critical thinking involves improving our ability to construct sound arguments and evaluate the arguments of others, minimizing logical errors and flawed reasoning."

What the author seeks to explain is that this type of reasoning is required for epistemic advancement and the formation of cognition, and that, absent from academic life, the result is an answer that seeks to satisfy what the student and/or researcher believes to be *the final and absolute truth*. In the field of human sciences, this type of reasoning has become the great evil of the century for humans, where there is no innovation in thought considered supposedly intellectual, nor is there room for broader and deeper discussions about the origin and development of societies, both mechanical and organic.

In this self-directed learning process, the student becomes autonomous in relation to what and how they interpret the reality around them. It's no use expecting all this to happen as if by miracle; it's the result of intense and continuous effort towards learning, based on the

analysis of facts, texts, contexts , and how all these elements intertwine to build the personal structure of knowledge which, in turn, will influence the formation of scientific thought.

Didactics, besides being a science, is an intrinsic condition that arises from intellectual conflict. In attempting to clarify or resolve these situations, there is an opportunity to expand knowledge about something. In distance education , this phenomenon should be fostered by the readings the student undertakes, and these should always conflict with what they believe to be their own domain of expertise so that, with their thoughts excited towards knowledge, they can expand their views of the world and the consequent opportunities for logical understanding of existence and its phenomenological events. Considering that, in the field of didactics, one teacher provokes and the other encompasses the discussion through this awakened condition of interest; however, when studying independently, this condition must occur from the prior analysis of the thought of the authors being studied, that is, it requires greater intellectual proactivity and a more objective response in the construction of intellect, whether directly and/or indirectly.

Knowledge arises from three typically human situations, and this needs clarification because human cognition is marked by conditions of abstraction; that is, what is learned, known, developed, and created is subjected to careful analysis and rigorous interpretation before it can be understood as something that presents phenomenological epistemic value to the individual. Regarding cognitive action, it is important to highlight that epistemological development occurs in three distinct moments; however, these moments are interconnected, and once the process is complete, knowledge itself is formed.

In processing these phases, *intuition comes first* , which is an inner vision, a * *tuere* * , an intrinsic interpretation based on personal values and the knowledge one possesses and masters, a first impression of the phenomenon one experiences and that affects them. Some will say that it is a reading of the world; but that is nothing more than an irrational impression of what one feels or sees. Reading demands a more accurate perception of the processes occurring around one.

This intuitive condition is inherent to human beings and has no connection whatsoever with mediumistic powers; it is a preliminary situational analysis based on the level of knowledge one possesses about the object and its psychology. Thus, it approaches the understanding of the target object of study of this work, which is the distance learning student , who, like any other student, will come into contact with theories, ideas, experiences, and phenomena that are completely foreign to them, and it is only natural that they face psychological resistance to what is presented to them by their teachers and also through their

independent studies, sometimes responding empirically, other times not, keeping their dissatisfaction confined to their inner space.

distance learning student, they are further removed from integrated interaction with their peers and teachers; becoming more subject to common-sense interpretations, unless they are willing to go further and try to understand, through classical authors, the answers they find during their investigations. They must learn to apply the principle of scientific refutability to their findings, because otherwise they will always be captivated by any theory that seems wonderful and enchanting to them.

Following intuition comes experience, which is a way of subjecting what has been learned to empirical tests that can validate or refute the learning and, from there, chart new paths of study, investigation, doubt, analysis, interpretation, and cognitive and mnemonic syntheses. All acquired knowledge and information must be subjected to criteria of judgment and value in order to understand and verify the extent of its pragmatism. This is a meticulous care that every student should take: to know if what they are learning is applicable to reality, if it is useful, or if it serves only as *trash* culture.

And, in extension, after subjecting all this to interpretation, *synthesis is produced*, which involves recording what has been understood after intense study and investigation; however, not reducing reality to one's personal vision, but expanding it until it can serve as a reference for other studies. Once the level of influencing others with their analyses is reached, the student is able to advance towards a solid and profound cognitive construction. During the academic training phase, the student is under the tutelage of their professors and tutors, being obliged to read and study authors who self-referentially consider themselves erudite and renowned, but who do not add anything substantial to their intellectual and creative processes. Therefore, improving synthesis will depend on an exercise of effort that goes beyond simple theoretical learning, obliging the student to develop a very broad critical thinking.

Below is a list of attitudes that distance learning students should adopt as a commitment to be achieved and surpassed if they wish to become competent professionals and impactful researchers in the world of science. These include 10 skills described and explained to clarify their semantic, theoretical, and empirical meanings, considering that learning is a phenomenon, not a simplistic event that can be summarized as pure cause and effect determined by the equation: *if you study, you learn; therefore, if you didn't learn, it's because you didn't study!* Between studying and learning lies an unknown distance that can only be determined by the individual who has traversed it. For some, it is less complex, while for others it may prove more intense in terms of challenges of various kinds. It is not about individual effort correlating with

results; it is about opportunities throughout life that directly affect each person, with greater or lesser intensity.

The skills presented for analysis and discussion are:

- Self-discipline;
- Self-awareness;
- Rigorous in their independent studies;
- Developing a culture of knowledge;
- Development of categories for semantic studies;
- Ability to become an independent researcher;
- Ability to interpret reality;
- Developing analytical skills;
- Developing interpretation skills;
- Development of synthesis skills.

Below, these issues are discussed , seeking to relate them to the requirements of academic training in the distance learning modality .

SELF-DISCIPLINE

This condition of discipline is a key point in the formation of any individual, because it is impossible for someone to overcome anything without a doctrine, without explicit rules to guide their pursuit. This issue refers to knowing what one wants and the subjective cost that this implies, directly and indirectly. It is not about demanding results or that there are deadlines to be met with a certain rigor, nor that without formal dedication to studies it becomes impossible to advance in the field of knowledge acquisition, and beyond that, it is not about acquiring it; it is about processing it within a rigorous intellectual spectrum, pertinent to each systematic content.

This action requires effort, such that there will always be a need for external motivation, in addition to that which is already necessary internally. In a regular classroom, there is a whole context of friends, colleagues, and competitors that push the student in this direction, coupled with the expectations of teachers, which makes academic discipline more rigorous than it would naturally be. In distance education , this condition is either nonexistent or not as impactful on students, which creates the need for the student to become their own main motivator, seeking

alternatives in their thinking that will propel them to overcome the challenges inherent in their training.

Self-discipline, in this context, refers to the autonomous drive to perform the ordinary tasks inherent in systematic studies and the course in question, to practice reading—both the mandatory curricular reading and the reading that serves as a foundation for broadening the understanding of academic and scientific processes related to training—and to adapt one's thinking to the formal norms of the language and to scientific thought. All of this must be achieved without external interference from anyone; the distance learning student must develop this unique vision that the commitment to their studies rests *solely with them*, undertaking the acquisition of experiences that can transform into broad and deep knowledge on diverse topics. Furthermore, they must be able to create their own independent study schedule and dynamically respond to the questions presented in the learning situations available on the teaching platform. All of this requires such discipline regarding time and dedication, diligence, and commitment that the final result is an intellectual construction that makes thinking itself rigorous in its actions and cognitive attributions.

It should never be forgotten that one of the greatest challenges of distance learning is related to the deadlines for submitting assignments and summaries required as part of the student's intellectual and professional development. Generally, these are short periods to develop the entire framework of materials, because it includes reading in its various stages, systematic analysis, interpretation, the search for theoretical and empirical depth, and also synthesis, whether in the form of reports, reviews, or assessments in their various forms.

What cannot be allowed to happen is for the student to fail to understand the scope of their educational project, for which they have chosen a direction, and to carry it out they must commit themselves deeply to no one but themselves, dedicating themselves exhaustively to finding answers to their most intrinsic questions related to their professional life and scientific interests; because it is not about acquiring a higher-level license; the interest must represent the acquisition of mastery over the technique and conditions of empirical applicability, being able to solve problems with extreme skill and competence.

This condition of self-discipline is an attribute linked not only to systematic studies but also extends to praxis, in the pursuit of constructing a thought process focused on the primacy of the "relationship of reciprocity and simultaneity between theory and practice" (Caniçali and Souza, 2019), a way of understanding objective reality from subjective reality. When the distance learning student understands what this means for their formation as a being of *Physis*, their sound thinking is consolidated in relation to what they seek as an objective in their life

and for their existence. Studying is not just about gathering ideas and concepts or discussing both as part of an expression of intelligibility; it is necessary to challenge existing ideas, presenting new hypotheses and destroying concepts when possible and expanding them, at worst, always aiming at the construction of new ones through discoveries that prove to be innovative and creative.

SELF-AWARENESS

The condition of self-knowledge is a plausible situation and, in a way, relatively easy to achieve; however, knowing one's epistemic limitations is something much more complex and cannot be achieved without due effort to deepen holistic knowledge about the systems that encompass life and existence and, to a somewhat greater extent, one must study natural phenomena to understand the limits of ignorance regarding their existence, occurrence, and manifestation.

This has been an intriguing point in the pursuit of knowledge, because when any reference is made to self-knowledge, there is a naive idea of knowing about oneself, one's attitudes and behaviors; which reveals very little or nothing about experiences and the ability to absorb them, process them intrinsically, comparing them with other realities and situations of phenomenological occurrences, enabling and enhancing their transformation into empirical knowledge [*what has been conventionally classified as skills and competencies*].

This *unique condition* of self-knowledge can only be achieved through the systematic study of phenomena, whether through empirical observation or the analysis of cases reported by those who observed and described them in detail, allowing the student to get closer to the facts; which at least allows them to know the factual conditions that are linked to things in nature and how they behave within a certain spectrum of induction.

distance learning , students need to be very clear about their epistemic limitations, which refer to difficulties in learning and understanding certain content linked to and/or related to specific subjects. Based on this self-diagnosis, they must seek to overcome their existing deficiencies in the epistemological field. This discovery does not occur simply due to a lack of understanding of the statements; they need to analyze the proposed content of the subject matter, perform dynamic readings, try to interpret the variables, connect what is in front of them with the presentation of the same content in other occasional or everyday situations, and thus determine their limit of factual knowledge [*empirical and theoretical*] about the phenomenon and/or object and what paths they need to take to achieve mastery over it.

The expression "self-knowledge" is a sympathetic way to determine the level of knowledge and recognition of one's own limits, which can also be interpreted as challenges to be overcome. It is true that all distance learning courses create a leveling space in certain subjects and/or sciences, according to the coordinators' level of understanding of this; however, this presents an opportunity based on a generic measurement that sometimes does not encompass very distinct difficulties and limitations that require very specific, restricted intervention, where one can also detect other signs of powerlessness or disinterest in certain content, subjects, and/or sciences.

It may seem somewhat strange and exaggerated to require the student, on their own, to identify all these challenging situations while proceeding with their didactic learning process, and then to correct such deficiencies. However, the distance learning model is designed under this epistemological format, in which the student is led to challenge their own epistemological deficiencies, and it is up to them to know them so that they can do so with skill and distinction. This, under no circumstances, means that the distance learning student is abandoned to their own devices; only that their choice implies facing such situations in the development of their intelligence, knowing when to turn to their teachers and tutors in order to clarify the obscure points in their academic journey that prove insurmountable without the support of a specialist in the subject.

This individual epistemological mastery leads to the formation of a differentiated professional; more astute and dynamic in the interpretation of empirical situations that require more or less effort of intellectual application in recognizing problems, attempting solutions, and developing proposals that are viable within operational, tactical, and strategic planning.

Rigor with their independent studies

In distance learning, one of the main requirements is the need for independent study, which must be carried out with extreme rigor. This is because the support of professors, tutors, and more experienced colleagues who research various topics is absent, unlike in face-to-face education, where daily interaction with various other figures arbitrarily fosters symbolic exchanges of knowledge and questions. Therefore, distance learning students experience a greater impact regarding the rigor of their pursuit of knowledge because, whether they like the situation or not, they are alone in their achievements.

When referring to rigorous independent study, this refers to discipline with schedules, care in choosing research sources, whether primary, secondary, documentary, or interviews.

Understanding the need for in-depth training, leading to a concern with defining themes and subjects to be explored in research, and creating index cards and archives relevant to the learning process, already reveals intellectual maturity on the part of the student and an understanding of the educational model advocated through distance learning .

The implementation of independent studies, as a task performed autonomously by the student [*and so it should be*], clarifying that otherwise this mischaracterizes the learning proposal, is more than an intellectual construction that leads to a higher level of thought, in Vygotsky's conception (2000); it is an acceptance of the norms pertinent to the training process adopted by the educational model; it is not possible to understand that Distance Education is a teaching mechanism where the student is left to their own epistemological condition. It suggests that the student should be and feel capable of exploring a path towards their epistemological construction, requiring greater individual effort and dedication during the process.

Studying independently presupposes seeking knowledge and authors on one's own, without depending on the guidance of teachers and/or tutors, and even when such guidance is given, it means being able to critically analyze the work after having read, analyzed, and interpreted it. This refers to being self-taught, undertaking the construction of knowledge that becomes autonomous, capable of issuing judgments and opinions on the problems and issues raised by society at any given moment, requiring clarification and solutions.

This behavior requires the student to develop a holistic, *unique* , and at the same time focused way of thinking, capable of processing information from various fields of human knowledge in a relatively short time, because the demand for information is growing exponentially and this *performance* is not likely to be interrupted, because the volume of experiences required for the individual to understand the process and synthesize it is much more extensive and profound than they can control; thus, they need to create independent, unique study and learning methods.

At this point, the interpretation of the term "independent" takes on the meaning of "singular," not found elsewhere, making it impossible to compare it with previous methods. This leads to the formation of a superior intelligence, endowed with a creative and interpretative capacity that is not deterred by challenges, whatever their epistemological and/or empirical dimensions. Becoming a free spirit in the field of education is a complex and daring task, because the current model almost obliges the student to follow a set of rules imposed by their teacher, something almost priestly. In contrast to this posture, distance education grants the student freedom to think and act upon phenomenological situations, based on their analysis and interpretation; no longer relying on theories generated at a great distance from the facts. This is

the transformation expected of the distance learning student , in terms of their achievement of mastery over knowledge, experience, and epistemology, so that the reality and psychology of the object, once understood, become opportunities for creation and intellectual growth, towards the construction of superior thought.

DEVELOPMENT OF A KNOWLEDGE CULTURE

Given the volume of information circulating constantly in society, it becomes very easy for students, with all their enthusiasm, wonder, and enchantment provoked by the aura of academia, to take any novelty as something relevant and of epistemic interest. In face- to -face training courses, this phenomenological condition inherent to the process can be minimized or exacerbated, according to the impression that each professor exerts on the students, running the serious risk of creating idols. In the distance learning modality , this situation is complex, even to analyze, from its occurrence to its empirical interpretation, because the student is, in a way, left to their own efforts of intellectual development and, at times, is more likely to connect with thinkers and theorists through their readings and literary discoveries.

When discussing the creation and development of a knowledge culture, this refers to the production of a body of theoretical and empirical knowledge in such a way that this becomes part of the student's own cognitive structure, deepening their scientific commitment to truth, where their discoveries and findings are subjected to criteria of verifiability and refutability as a way to achieve excellence and ensure that what they are defending is, in fact, information that can be added to their intellectual scope.

This range of theoretical and empirical knowledge is what will support your integration into the scientific community, forming a source of information that will assist you in interpreting the new theoretical and empirical challenges that your pursuit of cognitive development demands. This meaning extends beyond what can be understood as culture, in its strict sense, because " the significance of cultural expression goes beyond what it actually represents for human beings today. It has the duty to ensure that the link with the unconscious psychological heritage, with the object of value, about which and from which one has the possibility of issuing value judgments, is not lost. It is not limited to commemorating a historical fact, but its power, its persistence in surviving and directing the course of life and existence over time that unfolds over man and from his action, whether in the pursuit of maturation as a being, or as a creator and expander of new knowledge" (SOUZA, 2024, p. 15).

Within this concept of culture, a spectrum of verification is encompassed, considering what is convenient for the student to take as useful and interesting for their life and existence, in order to achieve a broad, deep, and pragmatic construction of what they propose to study and value as an epistemological foundation for their learning. This is the purpose of academic training in the distance learning modality, in which a solid structure is built, marked by challenges that, once overcome, open space to expand and strengthen one's own knowledge, not as encyclopedic knowledge, but as knowledge that transcends the limits of proposed understandings, reaching the space of synthesis, of the broad and unrestricted dissemination of what has been acquired, submitting all this achievement to public evaluation, through readings, critiques, and even a potential recognition of added value regarding the perspectives of social advances and paradigm shifts.

The construction of this privileged space of knowledge is a student's decision; however, there is little room for choice regarding whether or not to participate, under the claim that systems already exist in operation and adequately serve social and academic interests. The fact is that each society has its own peculiarities and inherent problems that cannot be generically shared under the scientific principles of social representation. This *sui generis condition*, presenting its limitations, serves only as a guiding framework in defining thoughts and pursuits for new scientific research ventures and intellectual development. This form of action leads to the creation of an informative database that later serves as a reference for other students and even for guiding broader and more complex works, where data is needed to substantiate the first steps of empirical investigation. This is one of the principles of distance education that has been kept out of the scope of its construction and its opening as an advanced learning method, and not merely as a teaching modality.

From all that has been said, it must be clarified that the essence of knowledge is expressed by what is broadest and deepest in itself, and with this, culture expresses what has the greatest added value in itself, generally manifested by the opinion of a single individual or group that manages to transform a singular or particular issue into a public issue, and over time such a historical fact ends up being lost, and what remains is the habit that education takes care to transmit in a generalized and decontextualized way (Souza, 2024).

"*knowledge culture*" is not documented anywhere; this already suggests that the creation of this key element for the success of distance education lies in the sovereign and irreproachable will of the student to create a space where they can turn to seek knowledge and results from experiences, in order to guide their studies, their decision-making, and their

questions regarding the research they can and should develop, with the intention of expanding their epistemic field.

DEVELOPMENT OF CATEGORIES FOR SEMANTIC STUDIES

One of the most pressing needs in distance education is the construction of a category of semantic studies by the students themselves, so that they can develop logical and epistemic improvements on the technical concepts of the elements that underpin their academic and scientific training. The original meaning of words, expressions, phrases, and even some stories are situations that undergo behavioral modifications, influenced by various contexts, notably society, political thought, linguistic restructuring, the science to which it applies, semantic-linguistic appropriation by other fields of knowledge, and in this variation of the epistemological process, it is up to the student to carefully analyze the resulting variants and how all this impacts their way of understanding the science on which they focus their learning efforts.

The goal is for the student to understand the symbolic and significant determinants of the terms used to define strategic thinking in the field of studies; because it's not about being intelligent; it's about having a very clear understanding of what is being written in relation to an object, whether subjective or objective. And, when the categorization of semantic studies is advocated, the idea is to represent the target objects of investigation and inference within their respective areas of creation, understanding their empirical meaning in their respective fields.

When knowledge of original linguistic structures is advocated as a way to develop the potential for formative and scientific thought, the aim is to lead the student to create their own logical chain of intellectual innovation, something of extreme interest in a world increasingly marked by technological advancement and which, with due regard to particularities, forces this group into a condition of submission to this artificial reality that they have conventionally advocated as normal, as if everything could be solved with *clicks*, thus dispensing with their innate capacity to seek solutions through logical questioning.

One fact that needs clarification is that information sources cannot be extracted from any dictionary, as if the public meaning of a word or expression determined its lexical sense. This informational material must be of a technical nature, respecting the paradigms of each scientific area in which the student is developing their epistemic construction. This leads to the fact that, according to the systematic dimension to which thought and informational interest are directed, meanings are very peculiar, requiring particular and directed studies aimed at leading

to the understanding and clarification of situations that are misinterpreted and, consequently, misunderstood, which generates historical errors that perpetuate themselves *ad infinitum*, interfering with the scientific training of the target audience.

In face-to-face courses, such situations can be mitigated through direct and daily contact with professors and other colleagues seeking to deepen their understanding of these fields of study; however, in the distance learning modality, students are subject to the constraints of their respective conditions of didactic autonomy, which imposes on them the imperative need to form *online groups* for the exchange of information or to develop this capacity to further deepen their appropriation of such knowledge, without being pressured by anyone in this regard; at most, they are guided to do so, and it is up to them to take the initiative and have the prerogative to categorize their field of semantic studies.

Learning in the distance education modality has a very particular set of demands, one of which is that this type of knowledge must go beyond simple theoretical knowledge. By taking into account the most original characteristics of words, terms, and social expressions, one has greater conditions for constructing a personal epistemic structure geared towards overcoming the challenges posed by society. This development of logical-semantic thinking is essential for the expansion of individual and collective knowledge, especially for integrating knowledge with experience and thus supporting creativity.

Semantic knowledge is linked to the development of scientific concepts, with the necessary clarification that a concept is tied to a paradigm, which can be sustained for a certain time and then replaced by a broader discovery that better characterizes the object in question. Semantic meaning will not change, although its use is linked to the sociological spectrum and the interests of each researcher in accordance with their investigative project. The semantic meaning of an object is tied to historical and philological fields; however, by ignoring it, the student misses the opportunity to analyze the epistemological and phenomenological contexts of variability that represent and foster the sciences.

It's not about knowing the lexical meaning of words; the point is to understand their sociological significance, what they determine as objects of value for society, and how they impact the psychology of the object. When distance learning students create and develop a semantic approach to the terms and expressions that characterize the fields of scientific study, they gain a greater understanding of the sociological behavior of peoples, such as their culture, customs, and values. This allows them to clarify how certain concepts were developed and even why some discoveries were not disclosed and other phenomena were not explained. This represents a particular condition for the student because, since their form of study is at an

autonomous level, acting almost independently, they themselves must generate this interest, seeking in classical literature the definition and clarification surrounding their respective target objects of investigation and intellectual appropriation.

Knowledge, in a general sense, determines someone's limits; therefore, understanding the epistemological and phenomenological nuances that have guided life and social existence throughout the centuries contributes to the formation of the scientific concepts necessary for learning development, expanding cognitive and intellectual fields. The student understands that the interest in education lies in the acquisition of knowledge; that is, all their creativity expressed through their work is nothing more than this: the *expression* of the supposed mastery they have over scientific subjects. But what matters is how they process this information that has been added to their being and how it impacts their scientific personal structure .

distance learning students , reaching this level is more likely and feasible because the demands placed upon them are more intense. This is because, in addition to acting autonomously in their studies and epistemic research, they also struggle against the veiled and traditional prejudice that outside of academic spaces and the direct transmission of knowledge from teachers, there is no valid knowledge. This subtly suggests that it is impossible for someone to become excellent in this learning modality. However, the phenomenological approach to sociological themes and subjects, analyzed and synthesized according to empirical scientific requirements, leads distance learning students to become capable of interpreting the reality around them and intervening in it with extreme argumentative and empirical capacity and potential, significantly impacting it.

ABILITY TO BECOME AN INDEPENDENT RESEARCHER

Becoming a researcher is an immense challenge, because it includes the ability to analyze, interpret, and then synthesize the entire framework of theoretical and empirical knowledge acquired and developed. Furthermore, this knowledge must be subjected to extreme rigor in order to validate its veracity and pragmatism ; indeed, this is a proposal that must be analyzed during the elaboration of research projects, because it involves a whole investment of ideas, individual and collective interests, and the application of evidence, both verifiable and refutable .

In the process of developing an investigative spirit, the student must learn to direct their curiosity, interests, and doubts towards questions that help them broaden their semantic and epistemological field, while simultaneously elevating their perception and understanding of the

reality that surrounds them. These questions include: What to research? When to research? Why research? What is the relevance of this topic to science? What is the relevance of this topic to society? What is the relevance of this topic to myself? What will be the impact of the discoveries from this study on the world? What is the usefulness of this investigation? What type of research can [*or should*] I conduct: bibliographic, empirical? Literature review, exploratory?

When the idea of becoming a researcher is discussed, it implies having a target object of interest, about which one can raise questions and possibilities for constructing inductions and deductions, in order to deepen knowledge about its psychology and its phenomenological aspects, both vertically and horizontally. In the specific case of an undergraduate student, they cannot be so selective, considering that they have a range of disciplines from all sciences, which they need to master for systematic learning and, consequently, approval for subsequent academic periods. However, this does not prevent them from creating a portfolio of thematic investigations, which is enriched according to their discoveries and the results of their analyses.

When referring to the ability to become an autonomous researcher, this presupposes knowing how to make the object choice in order to satisfy a desire to increase knowledge on a given subject, deepening the problems and creating new initiatives for clarification around the problems posed by society that require a solution, if not immediate, at least one that responds to the desires for expanding factual and phenomenological knowledge.

Distance learning students need to exert a greater effort in building their scientific identity because the course model, methodology, and strategy used for their training place them on their own account, at their own risk and responsibility, to become professionals worthy of the academic degree and license they have achieved. This is not to say that the University has no commitment to these students and to the development of their intelligence, manifested through various means of expression; it is simply that the epistemic investment on their part must be much greater, with professors responsible for providing pedagogical, didactic, and scientific information and guidance of such magnitude as to induce the student to surpass themselves and meet the challenges pertinent to the subject matter.

Conducting research presupposes the application of extreme technical rigor to the issues involved and to the target object of knowledge and clarification. It becomes clear that the intention of the investigation is to expand knowledge by applying mechanisms and instruments for data collection that help to explain what lies between what is *understood and what is not yet understood* ; that is, no research aims to clarify what is still categorized as *misunderstood*. This only clarifies that what is misunderstood, due to natural or artificial forces, highlights the absence of knowledge about it or the lack of materials or methodologies that could broaden

access to the factors of epistemic or phenomenological interference. This guidance should be given to the student so that they do not waste their time focusing on topics for which there is still no scientific and technical material or information that makes them accessible and understandable. Therefore, becoming an autonomous researcher requires mastery in very specific fields, and without adequate guidance from teachers and tutors, students end up collecting data without a causal link to the reality in which they are immersed.

It is important to highlight that, if the student does not have the conditions to become an autonomous researcher, they must develop this ability, because the distance learning methodology demands much more from them than the acquisition of theoretical knowledge or the encyclopedic accumulation of it; they need to know how to process it, transforming it into useful knowledge for solving everyday problems.

ABILITY TO INTERPRET REALITY

Reality, as it presents itself to human beings, is not always susceptible to authentic interpretation; it will always be an approximation, due to the various elements that permeate it, causing confusion. Among these elements are sociological aspects of all kinds, such as political interference, the economy, and the opportunities that each individual has or has had throughout their life. This includes access to good schools and good teachers during basic education, which provided a broader, more horizontal worldview through the epistemic acquisition derived from empirical knowledge.

Interpreting a given object means providing clarification about objective reality based on accumulated experience, acquired values, and also as part of the knowledge one possesses. This knowledge is responsible for determining the analytical capacity, interpretation, and synthesis of existence and the object of interest. The higher an individual's cognitive level, the greater their potential to understand what happens to them and around them, such as social changes. This understanding is essential for planning interventions through coordinated actions with others and also individually. Without the capacity to unveil the condition in which one is immersed, what remains is nothing more than someone who survives, despite their existence, without understanding the endogenous and exogenous impacts upon themselves.

Distance learning students present a condition and, at the same time, a need for greater depth in this domain, because, being directed towards a condition of study that occurs mostly independently, the interpretation of reality that they may adopt may be directly influenced by the authors they consequently adopt as the basis of their thoughts. This situation is a classic

phenomenological event that can become decisive in the formation of the individual's personal structure.

One mechanism that aids in developing a critical capacity regarding reality is the reading and study of works related to the fields of classical Sociology and Anthropology, which present the links between societies and human beings with natural and artificial phenomenological events, as well as their direct and indirect influence on them. Clear and precise guidance from teachers and tutors in indicating texts and authors is essential for the creation of this epistemic apparatus in the student, followed by periodic evaluations through specific analyses, using whatever means are available, in order to ensure that cognitive and intellectual development has reached the expected level within an analytical semantic field.

A student cannot be alienated from the reality that surrounds them, whether local or global, with all its human conflicts and consequences arising from these relationships, especially highlighting the issue of technological development which effectively alters the most intrinsic social relations, such as the marginalization of human intellectual capacity in favor of the mechanical capacity of machines to respond to the challenges and problems posed by society. This implies seeking the broad development of a critical potential that transcends common reason and enters the field of broad and unrestricted ethical questioning until one can get as close as possible to the essence of the reality to be analyzed and interpreted.

An interpretation should be based on maximum transparency and be as reliable as possible; by this design, it is understood to be based on sociological precepts and not on ideologies whose manifestation interferes with the judgment of facts, distorting them in order to justify one's own thinking and beliefs adopted as true. This longitudinal study should have the character of *explaining* the causal-nexus phenomenology, not justifying any type of excess that may, directly and/or indirectly, interfere with the student's worldview, preventing them from seeing nature in a broad and horizontal way. This specific capacity comes from the individual effort to analyze the various divergences that mark human existence in the macro and micro universe and even how they behave when induced by endogenous and exogenous forces. This is what is affirmed : to take as a directional object of study and interpretation the psychology of the object, that is, a greater understanding based on its behavior in time and space. This refers to the fact that reality cannot be interpreted by itself, much less by individual and collective concepts, each being applied in isolation in the process.

Since distance learning requires students to constantly subject their thinking to powerful self-analysis, the path to understanding the reality around them lies in knowing themselves, going beyond the surface in which they see themselves reflected and, from a considerable

distance, seeking to verify how imposing their image is on the thinking of others, causing those who seek a reflection on the surface to see them as an image of the knowledge they seek.

The reality in which everyone is immersed may not be the same that involves everyone, because some will tend to go deeper, to feel more the impact of decisions on their lives, to want more and, for this, they will be willing to sacrifice everything they believe in and have taken as truth for all the years of their lives, reaching the point of recognizing that they know nothing about nature and its phenomena, simply from what they call knowledge (paraphrasing Socrates [469-399 BC]), demanding of themselves that they seek more and, if they do not find it, they must create it through the interpretation of the phenomenological topologies that traverse them.

This condition of interpreting social reality is not about the innocent ability to read the world, which is about making superficial assessments characterized by common sense, in which what is most interesting to defend as the truth is taken as translated by the superior intellect of someone who, suddenly, has become endowed with a voice and a position. When proposing to interpret that which involves life and existence, the challenges posed are, firstly, to learn to listen to what the object of study has to say, and then to determine if it is relevant to time and space, that is, if it relates to what has been dimensioned in terms of society and objectives.

Often, this analysis leads to the interpretation that everything defended as superior values is, in theory, a way of maintaining power and manipulating human existence through the most outlandish beliefs, enslaving everyone under the tyranny of thought they have failed to control. Currently, this is being done through literature, where, as a condition of mandatory reading, students are induced to a particular worldview directed by those who believe that everyone should have the same kind of vision and interpret reality in the same way that suits them. This is not freedom; it is a type of intellectual slavery that distorts. This is the most intriguing aspect of distance learning, because students in this modality have the opportunity to engage in a deeper and more critical reading of reality, suffering less direct influence from abstract concepts, precisely because they are studying, most of the time, on their own initiative and at their own risk.

In the meantime, there is the problem of defining which reality this student will be able to interpret; the one that is relevant to them, that actually influences their life and existence, or the one created as a byproduct of image culture, produced with the sole purpose of distorting the understanding of the causal link between ends and means, a meaningless fiction created simply to justify the application of forces in some direction and on some object. Bacon (1561-1626) already warned about this risk, and what can be added is that distance education seeks to

provide a greater dimension of autonomy to the student and, when referring to independent studies, this is linked to their epistemic and phenomenological interests of a subjective nature.

DEVELOPMENT OF ANALYTICAL SKILLS

Analytical capacity refers to having knowledge and mastery of the field that one intends to take as the target object of study and, consequently, of analytical intervention. This means knowing how to introduce relevant aspects, breaking down the object into smaller parts until one understands each of them and their specific functions, and at the same time, how they act synergistically, causing the organism to be interpreted as something determinant in the sociological universe in which the student is immersed, whether physically or abstractly.

Blaise Pascal (1623-1662) already argued that one must first know the whole in order to understand how the parts work, and, in the same proportion, know the parts in detail so that one can understand the functioning of the whole. Therefore, one must be able to analyze both aspects, to the extent that the *desired intellectual development requires* it, and this desire cannot be determined by the student themselves, but rather by the academy and the professors who are involved in developing the curriculum.

distance learning students are individuals dedicated to a type of study that demands accurate analytical skills, it can never be imagined that, left to their own devices, they will overcome the challenges of understanding the phylogenetic reality that surrounds them. This capacity to investigate reality and approach plausible and enlightening solutions must be fostered by the professionals who accompany them, guiding them on the next steps to be taken and objectives to be achieved, all the way to discussing the results obtained and how they impact life and existence, creating complex situations and solving others when possible, and providing information that assists in decision-making.

Analyzing an object or phenomenon is a highly complex process that demands a very high level of knowledge and expertise, because it is not about inferring about the object by internalizing the perceptions that each person has, in a particular or singular way, about its phenomenological expressions. Characterization involves subjecting the object of interest to intense observation, in the expectation that it will reveal its weaknesses or points of impact on reality; that is, the answer comes from the object, and the analyst's role is to record what the object of study makes available to them.

Under no circumstances, during the object-phenomenological analysis phase, may the analyst leave their privileged position as an observer to infer, in any way whatsoever, about

what is on display, content presented and exposed by the object itself. This condition of neutrality is a delicate situation in science, where the student, given their intellectual and scientific unpreparedness, feels compelled to clarify something that is not being asked to do so.

Analysis is a technical procedure that follows data collection, whether empirically, through systematic observation of phenomenological events, interviews, questionnaires, and surveys, or bibliographically, through consultation of primary and secondary sources, archives, and accounts of experiences from third parties, using various available means. Through it, one seeks to gain a closer understanding of the psychology of the object, that is, how it behaves in certain conflict situations, which may be internal and/or external, depending on the moment involved in verifying the events.

To achieve optimal results in the analysis procedure, regardless of the object, it is necessary to maintain neutrality and sobriety regarding what is being observed, because any hasty pronouncement can become a negative bias interfering with the understanding of the object and its psychology, resulting in false-positive interpretations. Once again, it is necessary to clarify that distance education, which has resulted in the educational process through this modality, goes beyond technical and humanistic training, leading the student to a high level of knowledge and potential for critique, understanding it as an open public question directed at some object or phenomenon.

DEVELOPMENT OF INTERPRETATION CAPACITY

Interpreting something directly presupposes an intrinsic value judgment attributed to that object, based on acquired knowledge, not necessarily possessed knowledge. This explains why the dimension of knowledge one intends to express goes beyond what has been defined as the determining point of knowledge. Therefore, to develop a broad capacity for interpretation, one must dedicate oneself exhaustively to systematic studies, committed to the possibilities of epistemological gains that each experience can offer, directly and indirectly.

It must be clarified that interpreting is not defining something, any thing or phenomenon, a word that means *to put an end to*; that would be incredibly presumptuous; therefore, the semantic meaning of the term is to present opinions on what is taken as the object of analysis, adding valuable elements to aid in its elucidation, getting closer and closer to a broader and deeper understanding, and also providing opportunities for the development of new hypotheses.

Along with the ability to develop interpretive potential, it is essential that the student acquires the habit of reading for pleasure, because such action leads to the formation of a tempered condition for analyzing classic texts and their variants, as well as explaining the sociological environment in which they were constructed. First, one arrives at the interpretation of the text and, based on all the open questions it may leave, one moves on to understanding the political, historical, and phenomenological context, and then, ultimately, begins to trace and delimit the contextualizations intrinsic to the producer of the literary piece, the study, and its epistemological dimensions.

Along with the essential habit of broad and deep reading, grounded in classic, technical, and scientific texts, the expectation is the acquisition of a more robust and powerful vocabulary. Given the student's curiosity, they will discover the meanings of words, terms, phrases, expressions, semantic sense, and their presence in the lexicon. With this, it is hoped that the student will understand that the interpretation of something or a specific, sometimes rare, phenomenon involves the historical knowledge underlying the subjective fields of Anthropology and Sociology, depending on the time elapsed between their creation and the present moment, where the effects of changes in philosophical thought have induced alterations in meaning and perception.

Interpretation is a complex subject, which can refer both to the process and its result; that is, both to the set of cognitive processes that occur in a scholar when interpreting a text, a context [*of any nature*], and to the comments that they may make after reading and analyzing the target object of their choice. Therefore, it can consist of discovering the sense and meaning of something or of phenomenological representation. The student, given their still relatively in-depth knowledge of the themes and precepts of their training, which binds them to the technical principles of the chosen area, ends up taking the learning of the subject as something already defined and determined, without having to engage in the search for a broad understanding based on their own interpretation of objective reality. The distance learning student faces a more systematic challenge regarding this epistemological development, because they are, for the most part, dedicating themselves to their studies autonomously and, sometimes, independently, without rigorous supervision.

Thus, interpretation is a highly complex technique that must be guided in its application and empirical development so that, after refinement, it can become a theoretical tool applicable to the learning of other students. The process involves studying less complex texts, clarifying them based on their cognitive and epistemic potential; following this, concepts are expanded until a more comprehensive understanding of unidentified characteristics is reached, due to

various factors, the most relevant of which is the extent of theoretical knowledge about the object of study under analysis and lacking interpretation.

distance learning students, this requirement is more profound because they will have to find motivation on their own, without a teacher demanding that they go beyond the surface, surpassing their cognitive and intellectual dimensions and even putting both under scrutiny in order to detect how much they know and how much they have advanced in individual and collective epistemological development, because all academic production is permeated by the exchange of information between fellow students, however autonomously and independently the activities are carried out.

This condition of collective production already represents, in itself, an intrinsic need for interpretation, while at the same time revealing an opportunity for semantic study, because each party involved, generally from different regions, brings with it a whole context that is unique in terms of understanding and interpreting local reality, allowing an exchange of information that goes beyond curricular training, making it broader and more horizontal. In this, what is achieved is the condition of an epistemological construction based on unique phenomenological aspects.

DEVELOPMENT OF SYNTHESIS CAPACITY

Unlike what has been advocated, synthesis refers to the ability to create something new, unprecedented, from the analysis and interpretation of reality; it is not about summarizing complex things into situations or things that are more easily accessible or that provoke erroneous interpretations about the target objects of scientific interest. The complexity of synthesis is characterized by being something that brings unprecedented considerations about social and natural phenomena, allowing and providing advancement in intellectual-scientific thought.

education (EaD) is a specific field of formal education that aims to provide intellectual and scientific training that is as deep as, or even deeper than, that offered by face-to-face learning. It requires the student to develop attitudes and performances that go beyond simple cognitive learning, and their conduct must be marked by intellectual, cognitive, and scientific integrity. Therefore, when students are asked to synthesize the reality around them and the phenomenological events to which they have direct access, it is necessary to consider those they hear about as scientific evidence, given that they did not witness them firsthand.

It should be clarified that the fact of not having been an eyewitness to a particular phenomenon does not invalidate its occurrence; it only means that one should proceed with verifications and consultations in various sources in order to ascertain whether it is an impactful event on reality and how frequently it has been observed, to determine if it is not something of seasonal or sporadic occurrence, not justifying any type of analytical intervention, because its interpretation proves irrelevant to the macro epistemic context.

If an individual has witnessed a phenomenon, they are required to possess sufficient knowledge to interpret and decipher it, if necessary, as their mere description may not be sufficient to determine significant advances in the field of science and its respective investigative branches. The student's understanding must be of such scope that it can add something more to the epistemic understanding of the fact or phenomenon that was observed and recorded. This record serves as a point of comparison with other moments of phenomenological manifestation already recorded in various sources, such as stories, myths, sacred texts, romantic, classical or epic literature, and newspapers, all the way to analyses carried out by scientists at various historical moments.

As discussed elsewhere in this work, distance learning students are obligated to engage with this branching of thought and research from a wide variety of sources, without being prompted to do so by their teachers. This is because their education is based on their autonomous intellectual development, approaching an almost absolute independence in many moments of their academic and scientific training. This creates a dangerous precedent: the belief that this individual *should* learn on their own, which contradicts the logic of conscious mastery of education applied in distance learning. This logic expects greater effort from the student to become an autonomous researcher, capable of analyzing, interpreting, and synthesizing the reality around them according to formal scientific criteria. It is important to clarify that "synthesis derives from the Greek word *synthesis*, which refers to conclusions that are not self-contained, never resulting in absolute truths" (FAZENDA, 2003, p. 40).

This represents the main challenge in the formation of critical thinking, revealing that criticism means an open, public question directed at a specific object of curiosity. Thus, when discussing the development of ideas and the use of logic with a critical foundation, what is expected is a broad understanding of the target object, aiming to expand theoretical and empirical knowledge and, from this categorization, produce a conceptual vision of the objects and phenomena, which is interpreted as a synthesis.

Once all this is understood, what follows is the need to refine this knowledge and didactic precepts in such a way that the student understands the epistemic transformation to

which they have been subjected in the pursuit of intellectual and cognitive development. Distance education has become a requirement that goes beyond mere higher-level academic training; it is at the level of constructing an individual who thinks and develops, in the epistemological field, through their own effort. As they expand their semantic field, they also become more able to understand social phenomena and deduce the results that come from their empirical application. This action, if practiced in a coordinated manner, promotes the formation of a sound scientific personality.

CONCLUSION

Distance education represents, among many other things, a cultural revolution that has allowed countless individuals to earn academic degrees and others to expand their technical knowledge at prestigious universities, both national and international. However, contrary to what one might think, the requirements to become a student in this modality are numerous and profound, demanding efforts that go beyond the criteria stated in promotional brochures.

The sciences demand that those aspiring to degrees in these fields master certain intellectual and cognitive development skills, highly complex didactic attributes that become broader as one progresses in studies and in the definition of aspects, in which concepts become part of the epistemic construction, an essential condition for understanding the social and natural phenomena that characterize life and existence and, to a greater degree, academic life.

Thus, in developing this work, ten skills were listed that are essential for a distance learning student to achieve their epistemic goals, becoming a skilled professional in their respective field of choice, and also with the determination to analyze, interpret, understand, and synthesize the reality around them. In a society that constantly seeks to be innovative, being able to remain proactive and have clarity about all of this is a challenge that has never been so intense in history.

In general, an educational program aims to sharpen the student's potential for critical thinking, allowing them to create a worldview that proves innovative and creative; however, with distance education, there are details that make it a peculiar construct, namely that the student is, most of the time, on their own, without being able to count on the direct support of colleagues and teachers, and even if they can, there is the problem of distance and time for answering their questions, forcing them to become an autonomous and dedicated researcher, always needing to submit their own discoveries to the criteria of verifiability of what they have discovered, the pragmatism of the same, and the principle of refutability. Therefore, the

distance education student needs to create self-directed learning mechanisms in order to overcome their epistemic limitations and seek forms of phenomenological experiences that help them understand the results of their independent investigations and studies.

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